

Manifesto for the Construction of a Scientific Instrument to Measure, Discover and Access Worldwide Research for Free

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During my formative years as a scientometric instrument maker, I started doubting the official narrative—one that I had been propagating myself—that we were doing a good job by measuring with the mainstream analytics databases of the time. Albeit grumblingly, we bibliometricians bought the unchallenged assertion that these databases contained papers from the most highly cited journals and that we could purposefully measure the world's research with these data. During a [large research project on open access performed by Science-Metrix for the European Commission DG Research between 2011 and 2014](#), I discovered that this couldn't be the case. For all kinds of reasons, few having to do with how you'd go about building a proper research measurement instrument, no one was indexing citations from tens of thousands of journals, which inevitably created huge distortions.

Chinese database CNKI has more than 60 million scholarly articles written in Chinese. One shouldn't expect these articles to be citing the same journals as those being indexed in the English-language-dominated mainstream commercial databases, which contain 80 million or so scholarly journal articles. Very, very little—less than 5%—of Chinese-language literature is being indexed in the dominant Western databases. Similarly, mainstream databases are indexing too few journals from Asia, Central and Eastern Europe, and the Global South. They also exclude way too many journals from the arts and humanities, the social sciences, and even from the applied sciences. Journals with no English-language metadata are squarely being excluded. Excluding all this information for no particularly good reason means no one knows what the world's most highly cited journals truly are.

In the face of this, how can we accept the claim that modern databases dominating the field of scientometrics and bibliometrics are fit for the purpose of providing worldwide ranks of universities, countries and researchers? We simply don't have any instrument that would allow us to accurately rank these, even though, using existing technologies and know-how, it would be relatively easy and fast to build one. And it would be cheap to build too—requiring less than 0.001% of the world's annual gross expenditures on R&D, the world's GERD currently being approximately USD 2.5 trillion.

In 2011, I like many colleagues thought that there were some 25,000 journals the world over; however, by 2020, my team at 1science and I had assembled evidence that there were in excess of 150,000 scholarly journals, a figure since corroborated by [Laakso & Pölonen](#). I've been thinking about the population size of scholarly articles and journals since about 2010, and I still can't put a ballpark figure on it. Isn't it a disgrace that we don't know something as basic as this in 2023? Whereas physicists are using the [LHC](#) to examine minute collisions with ridiculous precision, the science of science has remained a largely stale undertaking for more than 50 years, where even today one can barely trust any figure with one decimal of precision. This is not due to theoretical or practical measurement limits other than the complete absence of a purpose-built scientometric database.

My mantra for the last 10 years has been that we need a database designed as a scientific instrument for measuring, discovering and accessing all scholarly articles published in every journal since the inception of the *Journal des sçavans* and the *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, which both started publishing in 1665. This mantra is as relevant as ever. The database would be structured from the ground up, carefully and [FAIR/y](#), to accurately measure research in all fields from all countries and in all languages, and would be accessible for free to everyone. It would espouse diversity, equity and inclusivity, or as Merton would have put it, communism and universalism.

In addition, we need to unlock all the publicly funded scholarly literature, past and present, and all the associated metadata, once and for all. The world's scholarly publishing industry earns a meagre USD 15-25 billion, a paltry 2% of the USD 800 billion of the worldwide public expenditures on R&D (PERD). Yet industry is continuing to lock in a large proportion of the knowledge being paid for by the public, despite OA mandates, transformative agreements, and the growth of green, gold and diamond OA.

The underlying economic assumption used to justify public spending on research is that scholarly knowledge and science are very difficult to appropriate privately, and hence they should be publicly funded. It is highly paradoxical that exactly the opposite is happening, with a relatively small number of firms privately appropriating public goods through copyrights at close to no cost. This is a shameful situation that must stop. We haven't gone nearly far enough with the open science movement. We need to completely overhaul the economic models of the industry, and the dominant forces in industry, their decision-makers and shareholders need to stop undermining the public good.

Speaking of industry, we mustn't forget about accurately measuring the USD 1.8 trillion in business expenditures in R&D (BERD). Hence, a publicly overseen database compiling a census of scholarly journals and articles would only be the beginning of a worldwide instrument for measuring, discovering and accessing scholarly knowledge and properly accounting for various forms of R&D and innovation. We need world censuses of theses and dissertations, patents, and trademarks. We also need comprehensive datasets comprising scholarly books (challenging because of unclear boundaries) and conference proceedings and abstracts (challenging because of their fragile, ephemeral character), and we need to consider new media, large experimental datasets, open-source software and so forth. All these datasets should be seen as some of the world's most precious public goods and should be open to every person, organization and company to help tackle humanity's most pressing challenges.

What are we waiting for?

A sizeable part of Éric's professional and scientific publicly available work can be found on ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4422-1054> and most of this is openly accessible on Zenodo